
EVALUATION OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTION LEVEL CAUSED BY CEMENT PRODUCTION IN OBAJANA, KOGI STATE

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ABSTRACT

*Topsoil often gets polluted as a result of anthropogenic activities. These activities produce fugitive dust that may contain heavy metals which deteriorate the quality of soil, water and air. Therefore, there is a need to ascertain the physicochemical characteristics and heavy metal levels in topsoil around large factories like Obajana cement factory in Kogi state so as to recommend mitigation measures to cushion the negative impact of pollutants in the environment. The location (geographical coordinate) of the factory was determined using geological and topographical maps, satellite images and Global Position System (GPS). Field observations, testing of water and soil were conducted to determine the effect of cement production activities in and around soil of Obajana environment. The data obtained was analyzed in order to assess the presence of heavy metals and other physicochemical attributes of the soil. Water samples were collected at random from the stream around the factory. About seven (7) soil samples, five (5) water samples and three (3) plants namely *Cynodon dactylon*, *Plectranthus Scutellarioides*, and *Muhlenbergia rigens* were collected from the same region. Heavy metals for which these samples were analyzed were cadmium, lead, chromium, manganese, copper, cobalt, zinc, Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) was used for analyzing the water samples while X-ray fluorescence (XRF) was used to analyze the soil. Results showed that the concentrations of cadmium, chromium, copper and cobalt in water were recorded above the permissible limits set by Federal Environmental Protect Agency (FEPA) and WHO. pH of all water samples was recorded below the neutral value. Concentrations of heavy metals in soil were recorded above the permissible limits.*

Keywords: Soil, Water, Plants, pH, heavy metals, Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, XRF, GPS

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution by heavy metals is very prominent in areas of cement production, and pollution reduces with increasing distance away from factory sites. The soil, air, water, and plants around the vicinity can be greatly affected (Peplow, 1999). Cement production is considered to be the principal source of environmental pollution due to heavy metals (Ademoroti, 1996). Waste generated from cement production gets incorporated into the environment, their heavy metal contents are absorbed by plants, air, soil, and water. When plants are consumed by humans, they can cause a 'silent epidemic' of environmental poisoning while the drinking of water around the iron ore mining site also affects human health. Heavy metal contamination of plants, soil, and water also results in deterioration of the quality of animal products as these toxic wastes can accumulate and interfere with animal organs and pose severe health problems ranging from cancer to heart and voice contamination diseases (Jimoh, 2006). The study area is Obajana cement Company and its surrounding communities. The company is located within the Lokoja-Kabba Geological Survey. The climatic condition of the study area is tropical and consists of 6 months (May-October) of the wet season and 6 months (November-April) of the dry season. Agriculture is the major activity of the people in this area. They cultivate economic food crops such as melon, groundnut, cassava, yam, tomatoes, and cowpea. The research is aimed at investigating the physicochemical characteristics of soil and water bodies in the vicinity of this gigantic cement producing facility.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The Obaja cement factory is located in Kogi State. Kogi State is bounded by Abuja to the North, Nassarawa State to the North-East, Benue State to the East and Enugu State to the South-East.

Figure 2.1: Showing states around Kogi State

Samples collection and treatment

Field observation of the site and detection of the geographical position of the mine and sample

locations using a Global Position System (GPS). The water, soil, and plant samples were collected from different locations and their GPS noted. Soil, water, and plants were sampled from within and around the iron ore mining site in order to identify heavy metals contained in these samples. The field observation was carried out and the position of each sample was recorded using a Global Position System (GPS). Data analysis using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) for analysis of probable heavy metal contamination in the samples. The pH of each sample was measured in order to test its acidity in the water. In total, seven (7) samples of soil, five (5) samples of water and three (3) samples of plants were collected. Each sample of soil was made of one (1) Kg collected from one (1) cm under the earth surface. The soils were collected by composite sampling (Random collection of soil in the area) and mixed up with a distance of fifty (50) meters from each soil sample collected, with their coordinate location using the GPS recording as shown in One hundred milliliter (100 ml) water samples were collected from underground, surface, stream, borehole and tailing water sources. These water samples were collected via the composite sampling.

Laboratory Analysis

All reagents used were of analytical grade. Standard solutions were prepared using these reagents in a laboratory apparatus (glass) which had been appropriately washed with distilled water, cleaned and dried to prevent contamination. Name of equipment: SKY RAY INSTRUMENT and type of Equipment Model No: EDX3600B X-ray fluorescence spectrometer applies XRF technology to conduct a fast and accurate analysis of complex composition. The system detects elements between Sodium (Na, Z=11) and Uranium (U, Z=92) with high resolution and fast analysis.

Water Samples Analysis

Surface, underground, tailing, stream and borehole water samples were collected from five (5) different locations, each location being 50 meters apart within the mining sites, as shown in Table 2. The samples were stored in clean plastic bottles, to which 5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to 250 ml of each water sample and evaporated to 25 ml. The concentrate was filtered using a cellulose membrane (0.45 μ m) and transferred to a 50 ml flask and 50 ml of 0.1M HCl, after which it was diluted to mark with distilled water. Heavy metals (Mg, Cd, Pb, Cr, Mn, Cu, Co, Zn and Fe) were determined using an Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) Model AA500F and Manufacturer Analytic Jena.

Quality validation

Reagent blanks were used to validate the purity of chemicals used for digestion; Certified reference material IAEA-SL-1 (lake sediment) was subjected to the same digestion procedure as the soil samples and analyzed to evaluate the accuracy of the analytical procedure; The detection limit of the FAAS used was also noted to help ascertain the limit of detection of heavy metals in the samples.

Data analysis

Data obtained from heavy metal analysis were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS 23.0 (SPSS Inc., USA) software. The means of the replicates and the evaluation of significant differences among sampling sites, sampling distances were determined using descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means were separated by Duncan Multiple range test at 0.05 probability level.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Physicochemical properties of topsoil around the factory

Table 1, shows the pH, organic matter and electrical conductivity of soil around the factory in the rainy and dry seasons. The pH values in the polluted site ranged from slightly acidic (5.1) to slightly alkaline (9.3). The mean pH value was; (5.1- 8.8) in the northern axis, (7.4- 9.0) in the eastern flank and (6.8 – 9.3) western side of the factory. Soil of the western axis was the most alkaline of the 3 axis investigated. The prevailing wind direction which must have led to the deposition of more cement dust in the west axis of the factory could have accounted for the recorded peak alkalinity in the west. This was corroborated by the report of Afeni *et al.*, 2008 on the prevailing wind direction in Obajana to be North westerly and the findings of Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2013a which states that the higher the amount of cement dust pollution of soil the more alkaline the soil will be since cement itself is alkaline in nature. pH of soil from the control site was lower (4.7) than what was obtainable at the study area. At 3km distance from the factory, pH varied from acidic to slightly alkaline while at 1Km, pH ranged from slightly alkaline to moderately alkaline. That is, the impact of cement dusts on soil pH reduces with increase in distance from the factory. The soil pH in the vicinity of the factory as shown in the EAA report before the commencement of full operation of the factory was slightly acidic (OCP, 2020). Owoleke *et al.*, 2020 reported acidic soil pH in soil of some communities that are about 40Km distance from Obajana cement factory. However, due to deposition of cement dust on the soil near the cement factory, a change in soil pH from acidic to alkaline occurred. This change can be attributed to the liming effect of cement dust as proved by Oludoye and Ogunyebi 2017. The soil was moderately acidic to slightly alkaline and slightly acidic to moderately alkaline during the rainy and dry seasons respectively. During the dry season, cement dust deposited is retained in the soil as there is no water runoff which washes away the deposited cement dust thus the higher soil pH recorded in the dry season in this study. This is similar to the findings of Eugene and Singh 2019. The modification of the soils in some sites from acidic to alkaline during the dry season could be attributed to the deposition of liming materials {CaO and Ca (OH)₂} which are often used for cement production. During the rainy season, the soils across the sites were observed to be more acidic than in the dry season. This may be attributed to the fact that cement dust is readily eroded by water and the presence of more hydrogen ions in the soil solution during the rainy season as soil pH is usually lowered by precipitation (Oyedele *et al.*, 2008).

Table 3.1: Total elementals concentrations (mg/l) of heavy metals in a water sample

Water Samples	Description/Locations	GPS Coordinates	pH	Cd	Pb	Cr	Mn	Cu
Sample 1	Beside the factory to the right/L05CKL	N07°36' 51.4" E006°19' 55.3"	2.49	0.04	0.37	0.20	7.12	0.17
Sample 2	Beside the factory to the left /L12CKL	N07°37' 00.8" E006°19' 06.7"	2.81	0.04	0.27	0.16	4.27	0.19
Sample 3	In front of the factory 500m/L13CKL	N07°38' 18.3" E006°20' 11.9"	2.64	0.03	1.07	0.22	0.07	0.17
Sample 4	Behind the factory 520m/L14CKL	N07°38' 22.5" E006°20' 12.3"	3.04	0.11	0.72	0.14	0.03	0.16

Organic matter of soil around the cement factory

As shown on table 1, organic matter content of soil of the study area ranged from 6.2% to 12.0%, with the highest (12.0%) occurring at E3 and the least (6.2%) at N2. Organic matter content of the control site was (10.0%). There were slight variations in soil organic matter

from season to season, distances from the factory and the three axes of the factory that were assessed. The relatively higher organic matter content in the dry season could be due to lower soil moisture in the soil during the dry season. Thus, microbial decompositions of organic matter were retarded during the dry season. The soil organic matter content for the three axis was in the order of North > West > East in the dry season and West > East > North in the rainy season. The relatively higher organic matter content in the Northern axis could be attributed to less cement dust, occasioned by the prevailing north-westerly wind direction (Afeni *et al.*, 2008) in the dry season. Thus microbial decompositions of organic matter was more owing to less cement dust deposition (Odoh *et al.*, 2018) in the Northern axis of the factory in the dry season. In the same vein, soil organic matter was slightly higher in the western axis of the factory in the rainy season because of the prevailing southwesterly wind direction in the study area in the rainy season (Odoh *et al.*, 2018). Soil organic matter gradually increased as distance from factory increases in both seasons. Cement dust is alkaline in nature and when it comes in contact with soil it interferes with both the synthesis and decomposition of soil organic matter (Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2015) thus resulting in lower soil organic matter closer to the cement factory where cement dust deposition is higher. Similar trend has been reported around cement factories (Oludoye and Ogunyebi, 2017).

Electrical conductivity of soil around the cement factory

Table 1 shows that electrical conductivity ranged from 100.5 us/cm to 119.7 us/cm. The control site had EC value of 95.0 us/cm. In the rainy season, electrical conductivity values were slightly lower than in the dry season. This may be attributed to rainfall and weathering intensities as well as to leaching and lateral translocations which is capable of lowering EC in the rainy season. This was attested to by the report of (Fatoba and Iyeh, 2012). Electrical conductivity decreased with increasing distances from the factory with few exceptions in the rainy season. This can be attributed to the significant amount of cement dust deposited on the soil surface around the vicinity of the cement factory. Variations of soil EC due to influence of cement dust has been confirmed by (Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2013). The irregular pattern of EC recorded during the rainy seasons may be chiefly due to the wash off of the cement dusts deposited on the top soil layer by rainfall. Also, EC was higher in the polluted site than the control site in both seasons. Cement dust contaminated sites have been reported to have significantly higher EC than in the control soil (Fatoba and Iyeh, 2012).

Table 3.2: Total elementals concentrations (mg/kg) of heavy metals in a Soil sample

Soil Samples	Description/Locations	GPS Coordinates	Mn	As	Sb	Ni	Pb
Light Vehicle oil disposal Soil	Maintenance Workshop Spent Point	N07°36'34.5" E 00617' 51.8"	512	176	9713	751	1173
Tailing Soil	Tailing Disposal Unit	N07°36'51.3" E 00619' 55.3"	82250	0	5383	860	188
Beneficiation Soil	Around the gravity and Lim Separating plant	N07° 36'57.0" E006°19' 09.4"	934	0	4824	438	496
Beneficiation Plant Soil	Gravity and Lim (Close to water thickener)/	N07°36' 57.2" E006°19'06.8"	846	0	7103	6050	355

Soil Stream	Stream in the coal mining Site	N07°37'00.9" E006°19'06.8"	14950	7775	587	0	
Heavy Vehicle oil disposal soil	Heavy Duty Equipment	N07036' 41.4" E00617'52.9"	1568	104	5496	548	976

Pollutant concentrations in the surroundings of the factory

The percentage recovery of heavy metals in the standard reference material IAEA-SL-1 (lake sediment) used for quality control and confirmation of the accuracy of the analytical process ranged from 91.9% to 110.8% in the rainy season. Detection limits of the AAS used were Zn (0.006mg/l), Cr (0.018mg/l), Pb (0.18mg/l), Cd (0.001mg/l) and Cu (0.025mg/l).

As shown on Tables 1 and 2, in the rainy season, highest (89.87mg/kg) zinc concentration occurred at N2 and highest (29.65) concentration of Pb was found at W2. The peak Zn and Pb concentrations recorded in the North and West axis of the factory could have resulted from a synergistic deposition effects from cement production operations, loading of trucks for distribution and traffic activities. This could be attributed to the high traffic density road that transverses from the north through to the western axis of the factory as Farmaki and Thomaidis, 2008; Wang *et al.*, 2009 have attributed substantially high soil Pb and Zn levels to vehicular activities. Also, the truck loading site is also located in the North-west axis of the factory. Pb and Cu are known to be part of heavy metals released during cement production (Carreras and Pignata, 2002; Banat *et al.*, 2005; Kakareka and Kukharchyk, 2011). Highest (115.87) mean concentration of Cr was found at E1, this significantly high Cr level in the vicinity of cement factory is consistent with the findings of Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2013; Al-Khashman and Shawabkeh, 2006.

3.2 Distribution of pollutants

The average concentrations of Pb varied along the sampling distances. While, Cu and Cr average concentrations decreased with increase in distance from the factory. This decrease in metal concentrations as distance from the factory increases is an indication that the metals were being discharged from the activities of the factory. In cement industries, the linings for the rotaries contain Cr, Co and Cu which could be liberated to the environment by wears and frictions (Banat *et al.*, 2005). Generally, higher concentrations of heavy metals were observed in the 1km distance than in the 3km distance. The heavy metals analysis inculcates cement dust originating from the cement facility for being partly or wholly responsible for metal contamination of soil around the factory. The decrease in the quantity of the metal concentrations as distance from the factory increases could indicate a link between the cement production and soil metal concentrations around the factory. Metals originating from industrial activities are distributed in soils by the atmosphere within a distance that depends on the size of particles (Mandal and Voutchkov, 2011). The highest concentrations of Pb, Cr, Cd and Cu in soil around the factory was obtained at 1Km distance and this may be attributed to the size of the particles vis-à-vis the proximity of this sampling distance in comparison to the others (2Km and 3Km). The contamination of the soil may be due to the close proximity of the farm lands to the cement factory. At close distance (1Km) from the cement factory, the soil exhibited lower Zn levels than farther away from the factory, this can be attributed to the mobility of Zn in the soil. The fact that Zn is known to have high mobility in soils has been reported by Luke *et al.*, 2010. All the heavy metals studied were found in significant amounts at the three different distances from the factory. However, the metals were concentrated more at the 1Km distance than at the 2Km and 3Km distances. At the 2Km distance, metal content

was quite high but not as high as in the 1Km distance and was slightly lower than concentrations at the 3Km distance from the factory.

The recorded concentrations of chromium at the 3 distances sampled, was such that chromium concentrations progressively reduced as distance from the factory increased. In cement factories (as reported by Banat *et al.*, 2005) the linings for the rotaries contain Cr, which could be liberated by wear and tear of the machine due to friction. Hence the source of Cr in the soil samples may be as a result to this process. Thus, the decreasing trend in Cr concentrations can be attributed to recent deposition of the polluting dust. The recorded values for lead in relation to distance from the factory did not strictly follow any particular trend as its concentration was highest at the 1Km distance at some points, and highest at the 2Km and 3Km distances at other point. Although, the concentrations recorded at the study area far exceeds what was observed at the control site. The influence of the cement factory on the observed lead concentrations around the cement factory cannot be ruled out as the production of cement requires a substantial amount of energy supplied by burning fossil fuel which in turn releases lead pollutant into the environment. This has been corroborated by several reports (Al-Kashman and Shawabkeh (2006); Ogunbileji *et al.*, 2013). Their regularity in the concentrations of lead as it relates to distance could be attributed to an interplay between discharge from the cement factory and vehicular emissions from the high traffic density road that transverses from the North, through the west to the southern axis of the factory. The concentrations of Zn and Pb could be attributed to the emissions from fossil fuels and vehicular emissions (tyre abrasions and wears) because of the high traffic density road that passes right in front of the cement factory (Fatoba and Iyeh, 2012; Asubiojo *et al.*, 1992). The higher concentrations of these heavy metals in the polluted site is majorly as a result of cement production as Bhatti (1995) affirmed that introduction of heavy metals into cement dust was related to combustion processes in cement production. Also, Ogunbileji *et al.*, (2013) stated that the source of fuel and raw materials used in the production of cement determines the amount of heavy metals in cement dust.

3.3 Pollution status of the different regions

Samples were collected from the western, eastern and northern axes of the factory. Samples were not collected in the southern axis of the factory as it was basically a rocky terrain. The quarry is in the eastern axis while a high traffic density road transverses the north, through the west to the southern axes of the factory. It is also worth mentioning that over 5,000 trucks load cement in the northern/western flank of the factory for onward delivery to consumers. Chromium, cadmium and copper levels of the sampled soil were high in the eastern axis, where the quarry is located. The quarrying activity must have accounted for their peak concentrations in the eastern axis. This finding is in agreement with the results reported by Al-Omran *et al.*, 2011 who reported a similar trend in metal concentrations in the direction of the quarry relative to a cement factory. Zinc contamination occurred in the northern, western and eastern axes of the factory at comparable degrees. This is indicative of the fact that external pollution sources of Zn occurs in the three axes. The observed contamination of the eastern axis by Zn could be as a result of quarrying activities, additional Zn pollution of the soil in the northern and western axes can be attributed to the high traffic density road in that axes. It has been reported that quarry topsoil are normally abundantly rich in Zn more than other toxic metals (Pb, Cu, Cd, Cr) (Etim and Adie, 2012). In the same vein, Zinc and lead in soils could be derived from industrial sources as well as from abrasion from tyres of motor vehicles (Al-Khashman and Shawabkeh, 2006; Garty, 1996; Carreras and Pignata, 2002). The highest concentrations of Pb, Zn and Cd were recorded in the north and west axes of the factory. This could be premised on the high traffic density road that transverses the north and

west of the factory, discharge from the cement factory and loading and offloading activities which occurs in the north/western axes of the factory. Loading and offloading activities re-suspends heavy metals laden cement dusts that eventually settle in the soil. Thus, high concentration of Pb in the north/western part of the factory was expected because of the synergy of depositions from cement production with the release from vehicular activities (Carerras and Pignata, 2002; Al-Khashman and Shawabkeh, 2006). Cd is derived from the mechanical abrasion of vehicles and is associated with tyre wear Kakareka and Kukharchyk (2011).

3.4 Recorded variations

During the dry season, the concentrations of the studied heavy metals were higher in the soils around the cement factory than in the rainy season. This could be as a result of their association with the raw materials (limestone, clay, laterite, sandstone and gypsum) used for cement production (Ogunkunle *et al.*, 2013). The deposited cement dusts were not washed away by rain water in the dry season. The elemental concentrations were slightly lower in the rainy season than values obtained in the same location during the dry seasons probably due to rain induced heavy metals dilutions and leaching into the sub-soil layers as researchers have indicated these heavy metals have the potential of being leached out when weakly adsorbed to topsoil (Zanders, 1999). Imray and Langley (2001) also reported that changes in concentration of heavy metals overtime in soil stratum may occur as a result of factors such as breakdown and leaching. This was noticed at all the sampled sites as the concentrations of all the elements (Zn, Cr, Pb, Cd and Cu) tested for were lower in the rainy season than their corresponding values in the dry season. This evidently could be suggestive of leaching. Leaching of these metals from the soil in the rainy season may have been enhanced by the higher acidity of the soil in the rainy season. Hernandez *et al.*, 2003 proved that heavy metals like Pb, Cd and Cu tend to leach more out of soil at higher soil acidity. In addition to leaching, reduction in Cd concentrations in the rainy season can be attributed to its high mobility (Vamerali *et al.*, 2009) and high solubility in water (Salt *et al.*, 1995). Cadmium has also been reported to be most mobile under oxidizing condition at pH levels below 8, hence the leaching of the solubilized Cd. Also, seasonal variation in concentrations of heavy metals in soils could result from breakdown and volatilization (Imray and Langley, 2001).

Conclusion

This research work provides data on the physicochemical characteristics of soil and water in the vicinity of Obajana cement factory. The effect of water, soil, and plants contaminated by heavy metals was possible through the use of X-ray Fluorescence and Atomic Absorption Spectrometer. The results revealed that the concentrations of Cd, Cr, Co, Fe and Pb in water were recorded above the permissible limits set by FEPA and WHO, while Zn and Cu were recorded below the permissible limits. pH of all water samples was recorded below the neutral value except tailing water 1. Concentrations of heavy metals (Mn, Cr, Co, Pb, Ni, Zn, Sb, Fe, As) in soil and plants were also compared with FEPA and WHO standards for heavy metals and in soil and plants samples. Observed concentration of heavy metals was above the permissible limits set by FEPA and WHO. Also, the concentration of heavy metals in water, soil and plants sample was also evaluated based on the distance from where the sample was taken to the mining site. The sample closer to the factory site had the highest concentration of the heavy metals considered. Also, the high concentrations of the studied heavy metals clearly indicate that the major source of pollution comes from the activities occurring in the factory. The work observed that many of the heavy metals are high in the cement laden soil than in the farms farther from the factory. It may, therefore, be concluded that mining activities contribute majorly to the presence of the heavy metals in water, soil, and plants in the area

while the heavy metals with low content in the ore may be introduced into the water, soil and plant from sources other than cement production activities. Soil pH is currently, slightly alkaline. The values of soil organic matter increased significantly with increasing distance from the factory sites whereas there was a decrease in pH, electrical conductivity with increasing distance from the factory. The heavy metal pollution of soil around Obajana cement factory was found to be slightly higher in the dry seasons than in the rainy season. Metal concentration of the soil was generally within the permissible limits except for Chromium and lead in some hot spots. The effect of cement dust deposition on soil was more pronounced in the areas nearer to the cement plants. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that if such trend of dust deposition continues, soil properties of a vast area around the cement plants are likely to change in terms of its physico-chemical properties. These changes will in turn have multiple deleterious effects particularly on agriculture, flora and fauna of the area in the near future.

REFERENCES

- Ademoroti, C.M.A., 1996. Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology. 1st Edition. Foludex Press Limited, Ibadan Nigeria, pp: 250
- Afzal Shah, Abdul Niaz, Nazeef Ullah, Ali Rehman, Muhammad Akhlaq, Muhammad Zakir, Muhammad Suleman Khan ;Et Al.(2011)“Comparative Study Of Heavy Metals In Soil And Selected Medicinal Plants” , Journal Of Chemistry, 2013, 5
- Agrawal S.K. (1999). Studies on the Effect of the Auto Exhaust Emission on the Mitragnapa Trifolia. Ajmer India: MDS University; Master Thesis.
- Aldennan J. K. 2002. Types and Characteristics of Non Heavy Medium Separators and Flow sheets. Mineral Processing Plant Design, Practice and Control Proceedings Vol. 1.pp. 978-994. Edited by Andrew Mular, Doug Halbe and Derek Barratt, Society for Mining, Metallurgy and Exploration Inc., (SME) Littleton, USA.
- A. Kabata-Pendias, H. Pendias, Trace Elements in Soils and Plants 1984 (Crc Press: Boca Raton, BCS, Incorporated estimates (September 2002) using the Western Mining Engineering, Inc.
- SHERPA Mine Cost Software and Mine and Mill Cost, An Estimators Guide U.S Department of Interior, Office of Surface Mining, The Effects of Increasing Costs on the Future Relation Between Open-Pit and Underground Mining, Michigan Technology University, Department of Mining Engineering 1982.
- Asubiojo O.I., Aina P.O., Oluwole A O., Arshed W., Akanle O.A., Spyrou N. (1992). Effects of cement production on the elemental composition of soils in the neighbourhood of 2 cement factories. Water, air & soil pollution, Kluwer Academic Publishers. 5758: 819, 1991.
- Awofolu, O. R. (2005). A survey of trace metals in vegetation, soil and lower animals along some selected major roads in metropolitan city of Lagos. Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 105:431-447.
- Bangbose, O., Odukoya, O., Arowolo, T.O.A., (2000). Earthworms as bio-indicator of metal pollution in dumpsites of Abeokuta city, Nigeria. *International Journal of Tropical Biology and Conservation*, 48: 229-234.
- Bankole, O. D. (2003). Assessment of particulate air pollutant from cement factory dust (A case study of WAPCO, Sagamu). *Journal of Advances in Chemical Science*, 6(4):142-152.
- Banat, K. M.; Howari, F. M.; Al-Hamad, A. A. (2005). Heavy metals in urban soils of central Jordan: Should we worry about their environmental risks? *Environmental Research*, 97(3)(2005)258-273.
- Carreras, H. A. and Pignata, M. L. (2002). Biomonitoring of Heavy metals and air quality in

- Cordoba city, Argentina, using Transplanted Lichens. *Environmental Pollution*, 17:77-87.
- Dao, L., Morrison, L., Kiely, G. and Zhang, C. (2012). Spatial distribution of potentially bioavailable metals in surface soil of contaminated sports ground in Galway, Ireland. *Environmental Geochemistry Health*. 53:94-107.
- DPR-EGASPIN (2002). Environmental guidelines and standards for the petroleum industry in Nigeria (EGASPIN), Department of Petroleum Resources, Lagos, Nigeria.
- Emmanuel, E., Pierre, M.G., Perrodin, Y. (2009). Groundwater contamination by microbiological and chemical substances released from hospital wastewater: Health risk assessment for drinking water consumers. *Environment International* 35, 718–726.
- Etim, E.U. and Adie, G.U. (2012). Assessment of toxic heavy metal loading in topsoil samples within the vicinity of a limestone quarry in South-Western Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 6(8):322-330.
- Farmaki, E.G., Thomaidis, N.S., 2008. Current status of the metal pollution of the environment of Greece –a review. *Global Nest Journal* 10, 366–375.
- Fatoba, P.O. and Iyeh, V.A. (2012). Heavy metal contamination of Ilorin-Omuaran roadside soils and vegetation. *Nigerian Journal of Ecology*, 12:18-27.
- Gbadebo A.M., Bankole O.D. (2007). Analysis of potentially toxic heavy metals in airborne cement dust around Sagamu, Southwestern Nigeria. *Applied Sciences*, 7, 35.
- Hernandez, L., Probst, A., Probst, J. L. and Ulrich, E. (2003). Heavy metal distribution in some French forest soils: evidence for atmospheric contamination. *Science of the total environment*, 12:197-219.
- Imray, P. and Langley, A. (2001). Health-based soil investigation levels. *Australia journal of pure science*, 8:90-102.
- Jaing, Y., Wang, X., Wu, M., Sheng, G. and Fu, J. (2011). Contamination source identification and risk assessment of polycyclic hydrocarbons in agricultural soils of Jordan. *Med. Bull.*, 77:54-67.
- Kakareka, S. and Kukharchyk, T. (2011). Towards improvement of heavy metals emission assessment methodology from cement production. *Russian journal of Ecology*, 43(3):67-80.
- Mandal, A. and Voutchkov, M. (2011). Heavy metals in soils around the cement factory in Rockfort, Kingston, Jamaica. *International journal of geosciences*, 2:48-54.
- Ogunkunle, C. O. and Fatoba, P. O. (2014). Contamination and spatial distribution of heavy metals in topsoil surrounding a mega cement factory. *Atmospheric pollution Research*, 24:374-382.
- Oludoye, O.O. and Ogunyebi, L.A. (2017). Nutrients assessment of tropical soils around a mega cement factory in southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 4(2):354-364.
- Owoleke, V. A., Fatoba, P.O., Theophilus, B. M., Olubiyo, G. T., Owoleke, O.S. and Akanbi-Gada, M.A. (2020). Impact of dust pollution from cement production on leaf anatomical features of selected plant species in Obajana cement factory site, Kogi state, Nigeria. *Confluence Journal of Environmental Studies*, 13 (2), 72-89.
- Oyedele, D.J., Aina, P.O., Oluwole, F. and Asubiojo. I.O. (2005). Preliminary assessment of pollution effects of cement dust on soil and biomass production. A Seminar delivered at 18th Annual Conference of the Nigeria Soil society, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Nigeria.